

EURL ECVAM Genotoxicity and Carcinogenicity Database of Substances Eliciting Positive and Negative Results in the Ames Test

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Abstract

The bacterial reverse mutation test (Ames test) is the most commonly used genotoxicity test; it is a primary component of the chemical safety assessment data required by regulatory agencies worldwide. Within the current accepted in vitro genotoxicity test battery, it is considered capable of revealing DNA reactivity, and identifying substances that can produce gene mutations via different mechanisms. Evaluating the predictivity of the Ames test for in vivo genotoxicity and carcinogenicity, when considered alone or in association with mammalian cell assays for chromosome damage and/or gene mutations, is an important endeavour. A consolidated EURL ECVAM Genotoxicity and Carcinogenicity Database, which includes substances that elicited a positive response in the Ames test in >700 substances was initially published and constitutes to date a collection of data that serves as a reference for a number of regulatory activities in the area of genotoxicity testing. Consequently, we considered it important to update the database to include additional substances and data. This update is under finalisation. We also considered it critical to expand the database to include substances that fail to elicit a positive response in the Ames test, i.e., Ames negative substances. A curated collection of 211 Ames negative substances was, therefore put together. The databases include a summary of complementary data available for other genotoxicity endpoints in vitro and in vivo, plus available carcinogenicity data. Together with the description of the databases a descriptive analysis of the data will also be presented. This also includes a representation of the chemical space formed by the Ames negative database with respect to other substances (e.g. REACH registered substances, approved drugs, pesticides, etc.) and a description of the organic functional groups found in the database.